

Genetic analysis of plant regeneration ability from cell suspension cultures of rice

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Genetic analysis of plant regeneration ability in rice was studied in 14 × 14 diallel crosses. The objectives of our study were to elucidate relationships between ecospecies and genetic properties of regeneration ability, to identify the varieties that improve the regeneration ability in F₁, and to evaluate the possibility of obtaining F₁s showing significant heterosis for both regeneration ability and biomass.

We used 14 rice varieties with diverse geographical origin (4 japonica, 4 javanica, and 6 indica) and their reciprocal 164 F₁ hybrids (seeds from 18 F₁s were not obtained). Callus induction and initiation of suspension culture were the same as that described by Tsukahara and Hirokawa (1992). For plant regeneration, after 7 d of suspension culture in a fresh subculture medium, 20 mg of cell clusters (200-1000 μm in diameter) were transferred to 300-ml Erlenmeyer flasks containing 20 ml of liquid regeneration medium.

Regeneration medium contained inorganic salts and vitamins of N6 medium

(Chu et al 1975) supplemented with 12 mM proline, 0.1 g casein acid hydrolysate L⁻¹, 0.1 mg NAA L⁻¹, 0.1 mg kinetin L⁻¹, and 5mM MES (pH 5.8). Three replications were prepared for each genotype. After 6 wk of culture, regenerated plantlets with green shoots of more than 1 mm were counted under a dissecting microscope. Data were transformed to stabilize variance using $y = \sqrt{x+1}$. A computer program for diallel analysis provided by Ukai (1989) was used for the statistical analysis.

Among the 14 parent varieties, the number of regenerated plantlets varied from 108.3 (Kele) to 0 (Lemont, CP231, Nan Jing 11, and Qing Er Ai) with a mean of 14.1 (see table). The number of regenerated plantlets for the F₁ was widely distributed from 164 (Kele × Banten) to 0. The mean was 36.9. Raffaello, Kele, and Qing Er Ai were parents in the crosses of 18 F₁s that regenerated more than 80 plantlets per flask. No regenerated plantlets were observed in 8 F₁s, either of whose parents—especially the female—did not regenerate. In contrast, even though both parents did not regenerate, five of their seven F₁s could regenerate. This suggests the participation of two or more genes in regeneration ability with complementary gene action.

The graph of array variance (Vr) and array parent (offspring covariance [Wr] for regeneration in 10 × 10 diallel table in which Lemont, IR26, Nan Jing 11, and Qing Er Ai were excluded from 14 × 14 diallel table because some of the F₁ data were not available) suggests that no non-

allelic interaction exists and that the low regeneration ability was dominant.

Analysis of variance of 10 × 10 diallel table showed that both additive and dominant effects were significant, as were reciprocal effects. No significant relationship exists between ecospecies and the above genetic properties. Among the 14 varieties, indicas Qing Er Ai and Kele would be useful for improving regeneration ability because of their significant high general combining ability and favorable maternal effects.

Heterosis for regeneration ability in the crosses of japonica/indica, javanica/indica, and their respective reciprocal crosses was higher than that in the crosses of japonica/japonica, javanica/javanica, and javanica/japonica. Kato et al (1994) also had reported higher heterosis for shoot dry weight in crosses of japonica/indica than in japonica/japonica and indica/indica using a half-diallel set from the same parents as in this study.

There was no significant correlation (r = 0.199) between regeneration ability and shoot dry weight of each F₁ hybrid, indicating that it was difficult to obtain F₁ hybrids with high heterosis in both characters.

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Regenerated plantlets per flask in a suspension culture of 14 rice varieties and their F₁ hybrids.

Female parent (origin)	Male parent													
	Japonica				Javanica				Indica					
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14
Akihikari (Japan)	17.0	34.0	24.3	24.3	42.3	79.0	29.7	0.7	23.3	24.7	20.3	55.3	3.3	31.0
Nipponbare (Japan)	7.3	20.3	52.3	4.7	5.7	1.0	7.3	5.3	44.3	22.3	43.0	125.7	12.0	39.0
Raffaello (Italy)	34.0	79.7	21.7	13.3	28.3	28.7	7.3	0.3	50.0	20.3	101.0	145.0	21.0	132.7
Bomba 1 (Spain)	1.7	1.0	8.3	0.7	1.0	16.3	0.7	0.0	18.7	11.7	63.0	92.7	15.7	5.0
Ketan Nangka (Indonesia)	4.0	37.0	12.0	8.7	3.0	4.7	21.0	0.3	31.7	12.7	19.3	80.7	13.3	30.3
Banten (Indonesia)	71.7	63.0	112.7	12.0	27.3	9.7	18.7	18.0	54.3	15.3	55.3	145.0	26.7	40.3
Lemont (USA)	18.3	4.7	41.7	0.0	- ^a	-	0.0	0.0	19.7	16.7	16.7	114.0	18.3	11.0
CP231 (Philippines)	2.7	0.0	13.3	0.0	10.3	27.0	0.7	0.0	39.0	1.7	70.0	114.0	1.0	5.0
IR26 (IRRI)	6.7	63.7	31.0	4.7	-	-	-	-	4.0	11.0	25.3	39.3	8.0	76.7
Jamuna (India)	7.3	1.7	10.0	17.3	29.7	42.7	12.0	44.3	16.0	5.3	3.0	22.3	10.3	35.7
Nan Jing 11 (China)	26.3	72.7	69.0	14.0	44.0	-	-	-	-	-	0.0	0.0	0.0	38.0
Qing Er Ai (India)	141.3	130.3	45.3	16.7	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.0	5.0	0.0
Dular (India)	67.7	69.3	74.3	68.7	76.0	58.0	75.0	15.0	29.0	32.0	40.0	50.0	7.7	14.3
Kele (India)	100.3	113.0	93.3	45.0	134.0	164.3	65.0	59.0	60.3	78.3	49.0	149.0	12.0	108.3

^a - data not available.

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Classification of Korean rice germplasm based on isozyme polymorphism

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Isozymes are important biochemical markers in genetic and plant breeding research. Isozyme polymorphism has provided useful information for classifying rice cultivars, thus enabling breeders to transfer desirable traits through hybridization within and between groups.

We analyzed traditional and modern rice cultivars from Korea using gel electrophoresis. Five isozyme loci (*Pgi1*, *Pgi2*, *Amp1*, *Amp2*, *Amp3*) were studied following the classification scheme of Glaszmann (1987). Zymograms were revealed following the staining procedure of Glaszmann et al (1988).

Of the 286 cultivars, 42 (14.7%) belonged to group 1 (indica types). This is the result of hybridization between indica and japonica types cultivated during 1976-80 as "Tongil type" in Korea. Most (242, or 84.6%) were classified as group VI (japonica types), which are currently heavily cultivated in Korea. Only two varieties were mixed. ■

Heritability and genetic correlation for component characters of yield sink capacity in rice

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Yield sink capacity (YSC), the maximum size of sink organs to be harvested per rice plant is a product of the number of grains plant⁻¹ (= number of panicles plant⁻¹ [NP] ×

Genetic correlation and realized heritability for traits related to yield sink capacity of rice.*

Trait ^b	YSC	NP	NG	NPB	NGPB	NSB	NGSB	GL	GW
NP	-0.449	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
NG	0.748	-0.690	<u>0.200</u>	0.959	*0.281	*0.544	*0.130	-0.256	0.472
NPB	0.041	-0.467	0.342	<u>0.426</u>	*0.507	-0.108	-0.122	-0.155	0.515
NGPB	0.435	-0.347	0.687	0.504	<u>0.040</u>	-0.787	-0.187	0.136	0.470
NSB	0.636	-0.286	0.642	-0.495	0.168	<u>0.179</u>	*0.368	-0.103	*0.319
NGSB	0.720	-0.294	0.619	-0.454	0.231	0.917	<u>0.129</u>	0.124	-0.074
GL	0.246	0.030	-0.313	-0.319	-0.181	-0.050	0.113	<u>0.270</u>	*0.153
GW	0.267	-0.559	0.147	0.268	-0.178	-0.047	-0.022	0.052	<u>0.773</u>
RGP	-0.964	-0.046	-0.384	0.899	-0.180	-1.008	-1.184	-0.393	-0.028

*Above the diagonal (underlined): genetic correlation coefficients estimated from selection responses in F₂ and F₃ populations of Nakateshinsenbon/Hieri. * = Sign of coefficient could not be determined. The data for YSC, NP, and RGP were not available. Below the diagonal: genetic correlation coefficients estimated from variance and covariance components in recombinant inbreds of Koshihikari/Nakateshinsenbon. Diagonal (underlined): realized heritabilities estimated from selection responses in F₂ and F₃ populations of Nakateshinsenbon/Hieri. *See text for the meanings of the abbreviations.

number of grains panicle⁻¹ [NG]) multiplied by single grain weight. Grain ripening ability, measured as the ripened grain percentage (RGP), is generally superior for grains on primary branches compared with that for secondary branches. Therefore NG must be broken into components: number of primary branches panicle⁻¹ (NPB), number of grains on primary branches primary branch⁻¹ (NGPB), number of secondary branches primary branch⁻¹ (NSB), and number of grains on secondary branches secondary branch⁻¹ (NGSB).

We estimated genetic correlation (rg) for these YSC components using two experiments. In experiment I, genetic correlation was estimated from variance and covariance components in 49 recombinant inbred lines of Koshihikari/Nakateshinsenbon cultivated under four environments. In experiment II, rg was estimated from direct and correlated responses in selecting F₂ and F₃ populations (Falconer 1989) of Nakateshinsenbon/Hieri. Realized heritability was also estimated.

In experiment I, YSC was positively correlated with NG ($r = 0.748$), but not with grain length (GL) or grain width (GW). A high negative correlation was detected between YSC and RGP ($r = -0.964$), perhaps due to the negative correlations between RGP and NSB ($r = -1.008$) and RGP and NGSB ($r = -1.184$). In contrast, NPB was positively and tightly correlated with RGP ($r = 0.899$). In experiment II, NPB showed a high positive correlation with NG ($r = 0.959$) and the highest realized heritability among the NG components.

In addition, NPB was not positively correlated with NSB and NGSB in either experiment.

These results suggest a strategy for developing a promising panicle type that realizes both high NG and RGP that consists of increasing the NPB to provide numerous well-ripened grains and suppressing the NSB and/or NGSB to not overproduce unfilled grains.

Chau and Bhargava (1993) demonstrated that the large sink sizes of high-yielding indica cultivars were mainly due to high NPB and high NPB × NGPB. The genetic nature of NPB must be understood more precisely.

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Heading-time genes control photoperiod insensitivity of rice cultivar Norin 20

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Rice cultivars grown in Hokkaido, the highest latitude area (41-44 °N) in Japan, flower far earlier than any other Japanese cultivars. Previous work on geographical analysis for heading traits revealed that the